

Speculation on Special Relativity and Wave Behaviour for a Photon and Free Particle Part 3

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In previous notes, we derived the Lorentz 2x2 matrix by assuming a particle at rest at $x=0, t$ and then enforcing $x'/t'=v$. In this note, we consider an arbitrary x, t for a particle with rest mass and a photon. In the case of a particle with rest mass, if it is at rest it can be at any x, t . On the other hand, if it is moving with constant speed one has: $x-x_0 = v(t-t_0)$. This equation holds in all frames with v being the signature of the frame. For $v=0$, one has $x=x_0$. Thus, the point x_0, t_0 seems to be like an initial point in the rest frame, but x_0, t_0 does not transform to an origin point in any other frame unless $x_0=0, t_0=0$, which is why $x_0=0$ leads to the definition $x'/t'=v$.

For a photon, on the other hand, any x_0, t_0 chosen in one frame transforms to the initial point because the equation: $x-x_0 = c(t-t_0)$ holds in every frame, i.e. c is frame independent unlike the case of v .

Derivation of the 2x2 Lorentz Transformation

If one has a particle at rest at $x=0$ at t_0 , then we have argued in the previous notes that in a moving frame it will be at x', t' such that $x'/t'=v$. The full motion equation is, however,

$$X-x_0 = v (t-t_0) \quad ((1))$$

Thus, using x'/t' implies that $x_0=0, t_0=0$. In other words, using $x_0=0, t_0=0$ in all frames as an initial point allows for one to have $x'/t'=v$ in all frames where v changes in each frame. In the rest frame, however, there is no motion and in principle one may use any x_0, t_0 , ignoring equation ((1)).

We show that a 2x2 transformation may be developed using $x_0=0, t_0=0$ such that $x'/t'=v$. In other words, if one has $x_0=0, t_0=0$ as a starting point in all frames, then $x'/t'=v$ holds and one does not need to use ((1)), i.e. $\Delta(x), \Delta(t)$. Then, one may define

$$\begin{vmatrix} A & v g(v) \\ B & g(v) \end{vmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

As the matrix acting on x, t to create x', t' such that $x'/t'=v$.

In Part I, we described in detail how this results in $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ where c is a constant speed which holds in all frames and $A = g(v), B=vg(v)$.

Particle with Rest Mass

In the above section, we showed that $x=0, t=0$ is a special initial point which is the same in all frames with constant v . There is no reason, however, to choose $x=0, t=0$ in the rest frame. Any point is as good as the other.

If one chooses: x_0, t_0 in the rest frame, then:

$$Xo' = g(xo+vt_o) \quad \text{and} \quad t_o' = g(vx_o + t_o) \quad ((2))$$

One may see that these do not satisfy $xo'/t_o' = v$. Furthermore, xo' and t_o' are not the starting points either because if one uses ((1)), then:

$$X'-vt' = gxo(1-vv) \quad (c=1) \quad ((3))$$

In other words, the initial point is $xo \sqrt{1-vv}$ and $t_{origin} = 0$ regardless of the value of t_o . Thus, xo, t_o do not map into a starting point (defined by $t'=0$) of the motion in the moving frame, although they are a point on the trajectory. One may see that:

$$gxo(1-vv) < g(xo+vt_o) \quad \text{for } t_o=0 \quad ((4))$$

If $v < 0$, then xo', t_o' ((2)) is a point to the left of the starting point $gxo(1-vv), 0$ time.

Case of a Photon

The photon situation is not the same, i.e.

$$X'-ct' = gxo(1-vv/cc) \quad \text{does not hold for any } xo, t_o.$$

At first one has:

$$X'-ct' = g(xo+vt_o) - cg(vx_o+t_o) \quad ((5))$$

Both xo and t_o appear unlike the rest mass case.

If one chooses $t'=0$ as a starting time in the moving frame, then $x' = g(xo+vt_o) - cg(vx_o+t_o)$.

Contracted Length for a Particle with Rest Mass

One may consider two so-called starting points in the rest frame, namely xo, t_o and x_1, t_1 . Then:

$$Xo' = g(xo+vt_o), \quad t_o' = g(vx_o+t_o) \quad \text{and} \quad x_1' = g(x_1+vt_1) \quad t_1' = g(vx_1+t_1) \quad ((6))$$

In the rest frame, the distance is: $x_1 - xo$ which does not depend on time t_o ((7))

In other words, x_1 with any t and xo with any t still yields $x_1 - xo$.

$$\text{In the moving frame, } x_1' - xo' = g(x_1 - xo) + gv(t_1 - t_o) \quad ((8))$$

If one considers $t_1 = t_o$ in the rest frame, then $x_1' - xo'$ does not depend on either t_1 or t_o . This then yields the contracted length, because x_1' and xo' are the lengths seen in the moving frame. Thus:

$$(x_1' - x_0') \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} = x_1 - x_0 = \text{length assumed in the rest frame} \quad ((9))$$

In other words, the person in the moving frame measures a length which is larger than what the person in the rest frame would consider to be correct. One may see from ((6)), however, that in the moving frame, one must measure x_0' and x_1' at different times, namely $t_0' = g(vx_0 + t_0)$ and $t_1' = g(vx_1 + t_0)$ (with $t_0 = t_1$). In the rest frame, one may measure x_0 and x_1 at any time. The result, $x' - vt' = gx_0(1 - v^2/c^2) = x_0 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ leads to $x' = x_0 \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}$ for $t' = 0$, which is not the same as the Lorentz contraction equation.

The question we next ask is: in $x' - vt' = gx_0(1 - v^2/c^2)$ ((7)), why does one have x', t' on the LHS and only x_0 on the RHS? In other words, why does all information about t_0 vanish? In obtaining ((7)), one uses $x_0' = g(x_0 + vt_0)$ and $t_0' = g(vx_0 + t_0)$, i.e. any t_0 may be used, but vanishes in ((7)). If one sets $t' = 0$ in ((7)) to define a starting point, then one has $x' = gx_0(1 - v^2/c^2)$. Now one may consider $t_0' = 0$ as t_0' does not appear in ((7)):

$$t_0' = 0 = g(vx_0 + t_0) \quad \text{so} \quad t_0 = -gvx_0 \quad ((10))$$

In other words, instead of considering x_0' and t_0' , one may consider an x_1, t_1 such that t_1 maps to $t_1' = 0$ and x_1' to $gx_1(1 - v^2/c^2)$.

The arbitrary choice of x_0, t_0 in the rest frame now becomes a constrained choice of ((10)) if one uses $t' = 0$, which represents the starting point in the moving frame. One may see that $x_0 = 0$ and $t_0 = 0$ satisfies ((10)) and keeps $x_0' = 0, t_0' = 0$, but otherwise this is not the case. By having t_0 as a function of x_0 , for $t' = 0$, one has x' at $t' = 0$ as a length which only depends on x_0 .

Furthermore, if one chooses $x_0, t_0 = 0$ as in the rest frame, this does not map to a starting point in the moving frame as $x_0' = gx_0$ and $t_0' = gv x_0$ instead of $t' = 0$. Only $x_0 = 0, t_0 = 0$ represents a starting point in all frames.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the equation $(x - x_0) = v(t - t_0)$ for both a particle with rest mass and photon and show that there is different behaviour for starting points. A photon always moves with speed c in any frame, so x_0, t_0 in one frame (as a starting) transforms to x_0', t_0' as the starting point in the new frame. If one chooses an x_0, t_0 in the rest frame then it maps to x_0', t_0' , but a starting point in the moving frame would be one for which $t' = 0$ and given that $t_0' = g(vx_0 + t_0)$, one has t_0 as a function of x_0 , so x' at $t' = 0$ is a function strictly of x_0 . In other words, x_0', t_0' is a point on the trajectory, but $x' - vt' = gx_0(1 - v^2/c^2)$ which does not depend on t_0 .